

Studies on Hydroxy Coumarins

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By condensation of hydroxy coumarins with formaldehyde and amines in (i) neutral medium, (ii) acetic acid medium and (iii) in hydrochloric acid medium two different types of Mannich bases have been isolated. Plausible mechanism for their formation in different media have been suggested. Some of the compounds have been tested for their antispasmodic and antihistaminic activities.

Hydroxy coumarins have considerable therapeutic importance¹. Singh et al² pointed that introduction of an amino methyl moiety augments the therapeutic value of a large variety of compounds and it is known that many compounds containing similar structural units possess antispasmodic and antihistaminic activity³.

In this investigation, the synthesis of similar compounds by the reaction of hydroxy coumarins (with hydroxy groups in the aromatic ring) with some amines like 2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole, dimethyl amine etc. and formaldehyde or para-formaldehyde in different media has been attempted. The media used are (i) a neutral medium using only absolute alcohol, (ii) acid medium using hydrochloric acid or (iii) acetic acid. Depending on the nature of the medium and type of amine two varieties of products have been obtained.

When the reaction is carried in alcoholic medium or in hydrochloric acid medium, the product is of the type of a simple alkyl amino derivative (I) and is soluble in alkali. In acetic acid medium when a secondary amine is used, the product isolated is identical with that obtained in the case of the former two media but with a primary amine a different product insoluble in alkali is obtained. This derivative is believed to be an oxazino derivative (IV) formed by the reaction of the initially formed alkyl amino derivative with a further molecule of formaldehyde and cyclisation.

Sethna et al⁴ have also isolated two similar products (one soluble in alkali and other insoluble) by carrying out similar reaction in alcoholic medium in the presence of a trace of alkali.

To explain the formation of these products, we suggest that in hydrochloric acid medium or in neutral medium, the Mannich base (I) is formed in the conventional way by the SN_2 or SE_2 mechanism⁵. But when the reaction is carried out in acetic acid medium, since the secondary amine can form a more stable ammonium ion than the primary amine,

1. A. Burger, *Medicinal Chemistry*, 2nd edition (1960) pp. 653, 1074, 1102 etc.
2. Singh et al, *This Journal*, 1960, **40**, 777.
3. Ghosh et al, *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 753.
4. Sethna et al, *This Journal*, 1962, **39**, 595.
5. Cumnug and Shelton, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1960, **25**, 419.

the nitrogen of the secondary amine gets protonated and thus loses its capacity to donate electrons as a result of which cyclisation is retarded. In the case of primary amines in the same medium, the nitrogen retains its electron donating property and forms a cyclic oxazino compound by the mechanism shown below (II to IV).

In fairly strong acid like hydrochloric acid the nitrogen of the primary as well as the secondary amine gets protonated easily and thereby prevents cyclisation of simple alkylamino derivative I to the oxazino product.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Methyl 5-methyl-N-2'-(4'-phenyl) thiazolyl amino 6-hydroxy coumarin: To para formaldehyde (0.02M) dissolved by boiling in absolute ethanol, 2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole (0.01M) was added gradually with cooling followed by 4-methyl 6-hydroxy coumarin (0.01 M) and absolute alcohol (10 ml) in succession. The reaction mixture was refluxed with a guard tube for 10 hrs. The pasty product obtained was triturated with petroleum ether and extracted with benzene. The product was obtained after removal of benzene, M.P. 210°.

TABLE I

The other compounds of the same type are described in Table I.

	Nature of coumarin taken	Amine used	M. P. °C	Yield %	Percentage of Nitrogen.	
					Reqd.	Found.
1.	4-Methyl 6-hydroxy-coumarin	2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole	210	65	7.6	7.4
2.	do	2-amino 6-chloro benzothiazole	245	50	7.5	7.3
3.	do	2-amino 6-nitro benzothiazole	256	62	7.2	7.1
4.	do	dimethylamine	265	40	12.0	11.8
5.	do	diethylamine	105	45	10.6	10.3
6.	4-Methyl 7-hydroxy-	2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole	183	42	7.6	7.5
7.	do coumarin	2-amino 6-chloro benzothiazole	235	52	7.5	7.3
8.	do	2-amino 6-nitro benzothiazole	276	32	7.2	7.0
9.	do	dimethylamine	240	40	12.0	11.9
10.	do	diethylamine	180	35	10.6	10.4
11.		piperidine	205	42	5.2	5.0

1', 3' Oxazino-3'-N- [2''-(4'' phenyl) thiazolyl] -2'-4' dihydro-5', 6'-7,8-(4-methyl) coumarin: This was prepared by the above method using acetic acid as the condensing medium.

The other compounds of the same type are described in table II.

TABLE II

Nature of coumarin taken	Amine used	M.P. °C	Yield %	Percentage of nitrogen	
				Reqd.	Found.
1. 4-Methyl 6-hydroxy coumarin (VA)	2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole	185	85	7.4	7.1
2. do	2-amino 6-chloro benzothiazole	135	35	7.2	7.1
3. do	2-amino 6-nitro benzothiazole	285	30	7.0	6.9
4. 4-Methyl 7-hydroxy coumarin (VB)	2-amino 4-phenyl thiazole	296	33	7.4	7.2
5. do	2-amino 6-chloro benzothiazole	120	35	7.2	6.9
6. do	2-amino 6-nitro benzothiazole	212	80	7.0	6.8

Antispasmodic and antihistaminic tests: The tests were carried on strips of guinea pig ileum in Dale's isolated organ bath. The spasmogen used for inducing spasm for evaluating antispasmodic activity was a solution of acetyl choline hydrochloride in a concentration of 0.02μ gm/ml. For studying antihistaminic activity, the spasmogen used was a similar solution of histamine acid phosphate. Of the compounds tested, it was found that for antispasmodic activity the compounds with serial number 1 and 2 in table I and 1 in Table II inhibited 50% of the spasm at concentration of 1mg/50ml. For antihistaminic activity, the compounds having serial number 1 and 2 of Table II at concentration of 1mg/50 ml blocked 40% of the spasm induced by standard doses of the histamine phosphate.

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